

OCCURRENCE AND DIAGNOSIS OF LEADERSHIP SKILLS IN THE STUDENT COMMUNITY

Mardiyeva Shakhnoza Amirovna

Teacher at the Department of Humanities and Information Technologies, SamSIFL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7957935>

Abstract. *In this state, the educational method of learning the leadership skills of students of higher education, the qualities and characteristics of students, and the help of several different methods.*

Keywords: *leadership ability, initiative, intelligence, scientific potential, student qualities, method and test in students.*

Today, at a time when science is rapidly developing, there is a greater need than ever for young people who are educated, have high scientific potential, are entrepreneurial, enterprising, intelligent, and have leadership skills. A strategic plan aimed at the development of human capital in achieving the ambitious goal of including Uzbekistan in the ranking of the global innovation index by 2030 among the 50 leading countries of the world was announced. This goal is to adapt the field of science to the requirements of the modern economy, and in turn, it is aimed at implementing fundamental structural, organizational, financial, personnel and infrastructure reforms regulated by the appropriate legal framework in science.¹ As our republic has been stabilizing its independence on a global scale year by year in recent years, its prospects depend on the development of today's generation into educated, spiritually mature people. From the years of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is on the path of its independent development, reforming the education system, looking at the process of personal maturity, development, spiritual perfection and mutual harmony of the interests of the individual and society as an important value, identified the issue of raising the training of scientific personnel to the level of modern requirements as a priority area.

PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", PF-6108 dated November 6, 2020 "On measures to develop the fields of education and science in the period of new development of Uzbekistan", No. 472 of the Cabinet of Ministers of June 7, 2019 "Psychology "Decision on further improvement of personnel training system and measures to prevent crime in society", as well as psychological-pedagogical training of students in general secondary, secondary special and higher education, state educational institutions This article is important for the purpose of further improvement of the support system.

Uzbek scientists in the field of social psychology have widely studied the personality of students and their development in the team as a separate research subject. It is obvious that a person joins groups in self-realization. Within the group, he interacts with people and can evaluate himself as an individual. A group is understood as a team made up of several people. On the one hand, the student group is a conditional social group, and on the other hand, it is one of the groups that, under the influence of the dynamics of development, should become a real group and community. It is of particular importance to determine the ways, qualities and characteristics of students

learning leadership skills in the student body of higher educational institutions. From this point of view, we determined the following tasks of determining the ways of learning leadership skills, leadership qualities and characteristics of students.

1. At the beginning of the experiment, to determine the type of collective culture in the student group and to determine the leadership skills and qualities of the students in this group in the control experience;

2. Developing a diagnostic model of student leadership skills in the student team prepare for a formative experience;

3. A program that develops leadership skills of students in the student community development and testing through formative experience;

4. Bringing the experience of forming leadership skills in students in the student community conducting diagnostics after the visit.

5. Formation of leadership skills and changes in the student team age characteristics of students and research goals are taken into account. Research as a result, to study the dynamics of the number of information about culture in the student body;

6. To determine the effectiveness of the program of forming leadership skills in students.

Based on these tasks, the relationships between the leader students in the student team of the Higher Education Institution and their personal characteristics were determined.

Psychodiagnostic methods were selected based on the theoretical analysis of each studied problem based on the principles of learning leadership skills:

1. The principle of taking into account the age and individual psychological characteristics of a student. This principle is based on the principle that, on the one hand, the mental development of a person corresponds to general norms, and on the other hand, the principle of taking into account his uniqueness and uniqueness.

2. Taking into account the emotional complexity of the presented documents and information. In the process of carrying out the exercises of the development program, creating a positive emotional environment in the team and eliminating the feeling of anxiety caused by the situation in students.

3. Taking gender characteristics of the person into account when planning exercises in leadership formation. When planning exercises, approach based on the biological and social characteristics of students.

Based on the theory of criteria and indicators for determining leadership qualities, we can choose the following psychodiagnostic methods.

Ye.S.Fedorov modified by O.V. Yeremin, T.A. Mironova, developed in Uzbek language by H.Karayeva "I am a leader" (integration of team interests and expansion of communicative relations) test was used.

Ye.S. Fedorov, O.V. Yeremin's "I-leader" methodology was used.

The purpose of using the above methods is: to be able to manage a team, to focus on its goals, to evaluate organizational and communication skills; assessing self-management skills; assessment of conflict resolution skills; ability to influence others; determining the ability to work with a group, etc.;

Each group becomes a team as a result of joint activities. Each community has its own culture and relations. The culture of the student community 4 are isolated. After studying them, you can determine which one exists in your group. We recommend that your answer be clear. Put

1 point for the indicator that is suitable for your group. Give -1 point for the indicator that is not correct. **Economic (Entrepreneurial) (TTM) group.**

- The main direction of the approach in the group: within this approach, the leadership training of people in the team is not technical, but managerial.

- The main principles of the approach: ensuring unity of leadership: receiving tasks from only one leader;

- adherence to a strict vertical of management;

- the chain of command is used as a communication and decision-making channel from the top down throughout the organization;

- determining the necessary and sufficient amount of control;

- the number of people subordinate to one boss should not cause communication and coordination problems; balance power and responsibility;

- ensuring discipline: showing external signs of obedience, diligence, strength and respect - should be carried out in accordance with accepted rules and customs;

- with the help of perseverance, personal example, regular control, to achieve the subordination of individual interests to the common work.

1. The second approach is "Organic approach (OTM)".

- The main direction of the approach: "Personnel management" and "human resources management" concepts were formed together.

- One of the main principles of the approach: Maximizing students' interest in work and management process.

- Making work the main means of self-expression of students;

- To provide the student with a job that is within the scope of his aspirations, ensures his autonomy and responsibility, and develops his self-awareness;

Communicate with fellow students and provide work that allows you to feel your importance.

- **The third management approach is BTM.**

- This team is driven forward by strong leadership.

- The leader determines the leaders and directions of development.

- Leaders are based on power and status.

- Disagreements and conflicts that arise in this team: threaten the stability of the organization, interfere with work.

- Method of solving problems: it is solved by clear and thorough thinking.

- Communication is formal and subject to rules. Students' wishes: subject to the interests of the organization.

4. The fourth direction: Humanistic. Participative (PartTM).

The main focus of the approach: according to the humanistic approach, culture is considered as a process of creating reality that allows people to see and understand events, actions, situations in a certain way and give meaning to their behavior. can be issued.

- Basic principles: organizational, collective culture.

Processing the results. The opinion of each group member is studied and votes are determined sociometrical. The sum of points is determined by the total number of students.

TTM maximum score is 8; minimum score -8;

OTM maximum score is 5; minimum score -5;

BTM maximum score is 5; minimum score-5;

Part TM maximum 2; minimum score -2.

The culture of the student body with the most votes will be determined.

Conclusion Several sociometric methods as mentioned above to determine the leadership ability of students in the student community possible

REFERENCES

1. The need to develop science, its current state and existing problems\ CONCEPT OF science development until 2030. Lex.uz.
2. Dune globalization process and the youth of Uzbekistan. A collection of articles of the online international youth scientific-practical and theoretical conference on the topic. T. Innovative Development Publishing House. 2022, 4 pages
3. Typology and factors of formation of teams.\Bazarov T.Yu. Personnel management. Tashkent 2021. 274 p.
4. Usmanov Sh.A. Mental abilities in students as the basis of their professional success. 19.00.06 age and pedagogical psychology. Developmental psychology. Dissertation abstract written for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Psychology, Tashkent, 2022
5. Gurbanboyev A.N. Psychological characteristics of students' self-activation in educational activities.
6. Saidov A. OILADA YOSHLARNING SOG'LOM TURMUSH TARZI TO'G'RISIDAGI TASAVVURLARI SHAKLLANISHINING ILMIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI //Involta Scientific Journal. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – S. 58-60.